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“A STUDY ON PRESCRIBING PATTERN AND RATIONALITY OF ANTIBIOTICS IN THE POST OPERATIVE PATIENTS IN A TERTIARY CARE HOSPITAL”

Prasad Honey, Kurup.B.Shruthy, Thomas Soumya, N.Upendra, T.Chaithanyakumar*

Department of Pharmacy Practice, Bapuji Pharmacy College, Davangere, Karnataka, India.

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ABSTRACT

Surgical site infections are confined to the incisions and wounds that were exposed during operation. Surgical antibiotic prophylaxis is the use of antibiotics to prevent infections at the surgical site. Prescription pattern analysis issued to determine the prescribing frequency of commonly used antibiotics. Rational drug prescribing is defined as the use of the least number of drugs to obtain the best possible effect in the shortest period and at a reasonable cost. The objective of this study is to assess the prescribing pattern and rationality of antibiotics in the post operative patients. A prospective observational review of the antibiotic prescription was carried out in the post-operative department of a tertiary care teaching hospital, Davangere. 150 case records of the patients were identified, assessed, evaluated and analyzed for the rational use of antibiotics for a period of 6 months. Among 150 prescriptions, 64% surgery were done in general surgery department, 26% were done in OBG department, 10.67% were done in orthopedics department. In 150 prescriptions, more no. of patients had received 2 antibiotics, followed by 3 antibiotics and most of them were given for five days of duration of treatment. Among 312 antibiotics, Cephalosporins 122(39.1%) class of antibiotics were frequently prescribed followed by metronidazole 76(24.35%). Most of the antibiotics were prescribed parenterally (96.47%). Our study provides insights into the patterns of antibiotic use, appropriateness of prescriptions and rationality of antibiotics in post operative patients based on ASHP guidelines and major, minor and moderate drug interactions, medication errors were found.

Corresponding author

Mr. Chaithanyakumar.T

Assistant Professor

Department of Pharmacy Practice

Bapuji Pharmacy College

Davangere -577004

Karnataka, India

+9845683133

chaitu.eishu@gmail.com

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INTRODUCTION

Surgery is a technology consisting of a physical intervention on tissues. The skin and mucosal surfaces provide an important barrier to bacterial colonisation of the underlying tissues. When these barriers are penetrated as part of a surgical intervention, there is a risk of developing an infection. Although surgical site infections are rarely a cause of death, they can contribute to a delayed surgical recovery, increased morbidity or debilitation, or cause catastrophic failure of a repaired wound or fracture.¹

Surgical wound infections are those infections which are confined to the incisions and involving structures adjacent to the wounds that were exposed during operation. Hospital acquired surgical site infection (SSI) is one of the major health problems throughout the world and is a serious complication affecting hospitalized patients. Among hospital acquired infections, SSI accounts for 14-16% of the inpatient infections. SSI is dangerous condition with a heavy burden on the patient has been associated with an increased morbidity, mortality and health care cost that have huge economic impact. The risk of acquiring hospital infection on hospitalized patients in relation to surgery is high, since about 77% of death of patients with nosocomial infections was reported to be related with post operative infections.²

Microorganisms can get access into a wound either by direct contact of air borne dispersal or by contamination. The risk of developing a surgical wound infection is largely determined by three factors: the load, type of microbial contamination of the wound and host susceptibility. Certain transient organisms such as *S. aureus*, hospital acquired methicillin resistant *S. aureus*(MRSA) and coliform occur on the skin with other commensals could easily contaminate the surgical wounds from poor hygiene.²

In the surgical department, a number of drugs (viz. antimicrobial agents [AMAs], non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs [NSAIDs], gastrointestinal tract [GIT] related drugs, etc.) are prescribed, but the AMAs are most frequently prescribed to prevent infections at the surgical sites.³ Surgical management cannot be completed without the use of antimicrobial and analgesic drugs because infection at surgical sites is one of the most common causes of postoperative morbidity and mortality.⁴

Antibiotics can be defined as the variety of substances produced by or derived from certain fungi, bacteria, and other organisms, that can destroy or inhibit the growth of other microorganisms. Antibiotics are widely used in the prevention and treatment of infectious diseases.¹ Surgical antibiotic prophylaxis is defined as the use of antibiotics to prevent infections at the surgical site. The antibiotic selected should only cover the likely pathogens. It should be given at the correct time. A single dose of antibiotic is usually sufficient if the duration of surgery is four hours or less. Inappropriate use of antibiotics for surgical prophylaxis increases both cost and the selective pressure favouring the emergence of resistant bacteria.⁵

Postoperative wound infections have an enormous impact on patient's quality of life and contribute substantially to the financial cost of patient care. The potential consequences for patients range from increased pain and care of an open wound to sepsis and even death.⁶ The goal of prophylaxis is to reduce the incidence of postoperative wound infection, and assumes use where contamination *might* occur, but has not yet happened. Empirical therapy is the continued use of antibiotics after the operative procedure based upon the intraoperative findings (e.g. leakage of a viscus). Inappropriate prophylaxis is characterised by the unnecessary use of broadspectrum agents and continuation of therapy beyond the recommended time period. These practices increase the risk of adverse effects and promote the emergence of resistant organisms.¹

As per the World Health Organisation, Rational use of drugs requires that patients receive medications appropriate to their clinical needs, in doses that meet their own individual requirements for an adequate period of time, and at the lowest cost to them and their community (WHO,1987).⁷

Prescription pattern analysis issued to determine the prescribing frequency of commonly used antibiotics. Rational drug prescribing is defined as the use of the least number of drugs to obtain the best possible effect in the shortest period and at a reasonable cost. The study of prescribing patterns seeks to monitor, evaluate and if necessary, suggest modifications in prescribing patterns so as to make medical care rational and cost effective. Therefore the aim of this study was to assess the prescribing pattern and rationality of antibiotics in the post operative patients in a tertiary care hospital.⁸

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials used:

- Informed Consent Form
- Patient Data Collection Form

Study design:

Prospective – Observational Study.

Ethical issues:

The ethical clearance for the study was obtained from the Institutional Ethical Committee of Bapuji Pharmacy College, Davangere.

Methods:

A prospective observational study was carried out between September 2016- in SS Institute of Medical Sciences & Research Centre, Davangere, Karnataka. The demographic details, Preoperative diagnosis, Proposed surgery and Therapeutic management were recorded in a properly designed data collection form. One hundred and fifty case records of the patients were identified, assessed, evaluated and analyzed for the rational use of antibiotics.

RESULTS

Among 150 subjects, majority of population enrolled were in the age group of 41-50 (20.67%) followed by ≤ 10 years (20%).

Table 1: Age wise distribution of patients.

AGE	NUMBER OF PATIENTS	PERCENTAGE (%) (n=150)
≤10 years	30	20%
11-20 years	7	4.67%
21-30 years	28	18.67%
31-40 years	22	14.67%
41-50 years	31	20.67%
51-60 years	19	12.67%
>60 years	13	8.67%
TOTAL	150	100%

This study was done in OBG, Orthopaedic and General surgery departments, among these majority of patients undergone surgery were from general surgery department 96(63.33%) followed by OBG 39(26%) and Orthopaedics 16(10.67%).

Table 2: Department wise categorization of study population.

DEPARTMENT	NO. OF PATIENT	PERCENTAGE (%) (n=150)
GENERAL	95	63.33%
OBG	39	26%
ORTHOPEADICS	16	10.67%

Table 3 shows that in a total of 150 prescriptions, 69 (46%) prescriptions were given with 2 antibiotics followed by 39 (26%) prescriptions with 3 antibiotics, 38 (25.33%) prescriptions with 1 antibiotic, 3 (2%) prescriptions with 5 antibiotics and only 1 (0.67%) prescription with 4 antibiotics respectively.

Table 3: Post-Operative in-patient exposure to antibiotics.

NUMBER OF ANTIBIOTIC (s)/PATIENT	NUMBER OF PRESCRIPTIONS	PERCENTAGE (%) (n=150)	TOTAL NUMBER OF ANTIBIOTICS PRESCRIBED (n=312)
1	38	25.33%	38
2	69	46%	138
3	39	26%	117
4	1	0.67%	4
5	3	2%	15
TOTAL ANTIBIOTICS	150	100%	312

Out of 150 prescription, total number of antibiotics prescribed were 312, among that 153 (49.03%) antibiotics were given for duration of 5 days followed by 78 (25%) antibiotics for 7 days, 44 (14.1%) antibiotics for 3 days, 12 (3.84%) antibiotics for 4 days, 8 (2.56%) antibiotics for 1 and 2 days, 5 (1.6%) antibiotics for 6 days and 2 (0.64%) antibiotics for 8 and 10 days respectively.

Table 4: Duration of antibiotic treatment with respect to number of antibiotics prescribed.

DURATION OF ANTIBIOTICS TREATMENT(DAYS)	NO.OF ANTIBIOTIC PRESCRIBED	PERCENTAGE(%) (n=312)
1	8	2.56%
2	8	2.56%
3	44	14.1%
4	12	3.84%
5	153	49.03%
6	5	1.60%
7	78	25%
8	2	0.64%
≥9	2	0.64%
TOTAL	312	100%

A total number of 312 antibiotics were prescribed in our study ,among that most frequently prescribed classes of antibiotics were Cephalosporins 122 (39.1%) followed by Metronidazole 78 (25%), Aminoglycosides 71 (22.76%) and penicillin 23 (7.37%) but least no of antibiotics was amongst carbapenem group ie 3 (0.96%).

Table 5: Prescribing pattern of antibiotics.

ANTIBIOTIC CLASS	NUMBER OF ANTIBIOTICS	PERCENTAGE(%) (n=312)
CEPHALOSPORINS	122	39.1%
PENICILLIN	23	7.37%
AMINOGLYCOSIDES	39	12.5%
FLUOROQUINOLONES	8	2.56%
TETRACYCLINES	38	12.17%
CARBAPENEMS	3	0.96%
METRONIDAZOLE	76	24.35%
LINCOSAMIDES	3	0.96%
TOTAL	312	100%

In this study , it was found that 312 antibiotics were used in total of 150 patients. Among 312 antibiotics, Metronidazole 78 (25%) has the highest rate of concordance with ASHP guidelines followed by Ceftriaxone 49 (15.71%) as shown in Table no 6.

Table 6: Antibiotics used in various departments for surgical prophylaxis as per ASHP guidelines.

SL NO	ANTIBIOTICS	GENERAL SURGERY			TOTAL	RATE OF CONCORDANCE WITH ASHP GUIDELINES (%)
		OBG	ORTHOPAEDIC	GENERAL SURGERY		
1	Metronidazole	37	2	39	78	25
2	Amikacin	3	10	26	39	12.5
3	Ceftriaxone	6	8	35	49	15.71
4	Cefixime	2	0	4	6	1.92
5	Cefuroxime	5	3	7	15	4.81
6	Cefoperazone	0	2	3	5	1.6
7	Cefotaxim	23	2	21	46	14.74
8	Ceftazidime + Tazobactam	0	0	1	1	0.32
9	Gentamycin	26	0	6	32	10.26
10	Levofloxacin	1	0	1	2	0.64
11	Pipperacillin + Tazobactam	0	3	16	19	6.1
12	Linezolid	0	0	4	4	1.3
13	Amoxicillin	0	0	4	4	1.3
14	Clindamycin	0	0	6	6	1.92
15	Moxifloxacin	0	0	3	3	0.96
16	Meropenem	0	0	3	3	0.96

In our study, among 150 cases collected during the study period, the common surgeries performed includes Hysterectomy(28), Appendectomy(13), Fractures(14), Laparotomy(17), Herniotomy(9), Surgical debridement(7), Palatoplasty(8), HysteroLaparoscopy(5), Vascular repair(5), Craniotomy(4), Fasciotomy(3), Quadrantectomy(2), Abdominal tubectomy(2), Bone grafting(2), Laproscopic ovarian cystectomy(2), Laparotomy(cystectomy, salpingectomy)(2) and others(27). Majority of the patients were undergone Hysterectomy followed by fractures and appendectomy etc.

Table 7: Common Surgeries.

DEPARTMENT	SURGERIES	NO OF CASES	PERCENTAGE (%)
OBG	1. Hysterectomy	28	18.67
	2. Diagnostic Hysteroscopy	5	3.33
	3. Laparotomy (cystectomy, salpingectomy)	2	1.33
	4. Abdominal Tubectomy	2	1.33
	5. Laproscopic Ovarian Cystectomy	2	1.33
ORTHOPAEDIC	1. Fractures	14	9.33
	2. Bone Grafting	2	1.33
GENERAL	1. Appendectomy	13	8.66
	2. Laparotomy(perforation, Hirschprung disease, splenic injury, carcinoma)	17	11.33
	3. Debridement	7	4.67
	4. Vascular Repair	5	3.33
	5. Craniotomy	4	2.67
	6. Palatoplasty	8	5.33
	7. Herniotomy	9	6
	8. Quadrantectomy	2	1.33
	9. Fasciotomy	3	2
	10. Others	27	18

Out of 150 prescriptions, a total of 119 drug-drug interactions were found which include minor, moderate, and major interaction. Among these, minor interactions 67 (44.67%) were mostly found followed by moderate 49 (32.67%) and major 3 (2%) respectively.

Table 8: Drug Interactions.

TYPE OF INTERACTIONS	NUMBER OF INTERACTION	PERCENTAGE OF INTERACTION(%)
MAJOR	3	2%
MODERATE	49	32.67%
MINOR	67	44.67%
TOTAL	119	79.33%

Out of 150 prescriptions included for the study, 24 (16%) prescriptions were found to have Medication errors out of which 22 (14.67%) contribute Dose errors followed by 2 (1.33%) duplication errors.

Table 9: Antibiotics usage on rationality parameters.

MEDICATION ERRORS	NUMBER OF ERRORS	PERCENTAGE OF ERRORS
DUPLICATION ERRORS	2	1.33%
DOSE ERRORS	22	14.67%
TOTAL	24	16%

DISCUSSION

Antibiotics are the most widely prescribed drug among today's scenario in saving life due to the increased incidence of infections. Irrational prescriptions of antimicrobial agents can lead to the emergence of high antimicrobial resistance which will in turn increase the treatment cost and harm the human life. Due to the inadequate data and guidelines for surgery prophylaxis, there is a need for extensive studies to develop a baseline data on utilization pattern of antibiotics in surgery practice.⁹ Surgical procedures needs antimicrobial coverage to avoid postoperative infective complications, but it is observed that unnecessary use of antimicrobials is also common. There are many reasons for such a type of trend such as the desire to avoid postoperative complications, to get early relief, claim of lack of time for of investigations or lack of sufficient microbiological laboratory infrastructure, and belief and experience of surgeon over a number of antimicrobials.⁴

For our study, we have adopted American society of health-system pharmacist (ASHP) guidelines as reference. These guidelines are intended to provide practitioners with a standardized approach to the rational, safe, and effective use of antimicrobial agents for the prevention of surgical-site infections (SSIs) based on currently available clinical evidence and emerging issues¹⁰.

Details of the patients included in the study:

The overall data of 150 patients who underwent surgery in the General surgery, OBG, And Orthopaedics departments of a tertiary care teaching hospital were collected.

Demographic characteristics of patients:

Gender:

In our study male preponderance was seen. Similar results were observed in the study conducted by Bangari Anilkumar et al^[1] and P. Maheshwari et al^[11].

Age:

Patients of all age groups were taken into the study and majority of the patients enrolled were between 41-50(20.67%) years of age group. Similar results were observed in the study conducted by Sumit Kumar et al^[12].

Department wise categorization of study population:

The study indicates that majority of patients undergone surgery were from general surgery department 95(63.33%) followed by OBG 39(26%) and orthopaedics 16(10.67%). Studies conducted by Sumit Kumar et al^[12] and Al-Azzam et al^[13] showed similar results. Hysterectomy (18.67%) was the most frequent performed surgery type followed by laparotomy (11.33%), fractures (9.33%), appendectomy (8.66%) and other procedures(18%).¹⁴

Post-operative in-patient exposure to antibiotics:

Out of 150 prescriptions, the major prescriptions 69 (46%) were prescribed with two drugs, while three antibiotics were prescribed in 39 (26%) cases and single antibiotic was prescribed in 38(25.33%) cases. Similar results observed in the study conducted by Bansali NB et al^[15], Sumitkumar et al^[12] and Dr Sneha Sussana et al^[16].

Commonly prescribed antibiotics:

Out of 312 prescribed surgical antibiotic prophylaxis, the mostly preferred antibiotic was cephalosporin(39.1%) followed by metronidazole (24.35%), aminoglycosides (12.5%), tetracyclines (12.17%), penicillin (7.37%) and the least being other antibiotics like fluoroquinolones (2.56%), carbapenems (0.96%) and lincosamides (0.96%). Studies conducted by Ayesha Parveen et al^[6] and SapnaPatil et al^[17] showed similar results. This result was less as revealed by Bhansali et al^[15](74.73%).

Antibiotics used in various departments for surgical prophylaxis as per ASHP guidelines

Out of 312 antibiotics recommended, metronidazole (25%) has the highest rate of concordance with ASHP guidelines followed by ceftriaxone (15.71%) and cefotaxime (14.74%). But the study conducted by Sumit Kumar et al^[12] reported that out of 269 antibiotics recommended, cefotaxim (38.29%) has the highest rate of concordance with ASHP guidelines followed by metronidazole (27%).

Duration of antibiotic treatment with respect to number of antibiotics prescribed.

Out of 150 prescription, total number of antibiotics prescribed is 312, among that 153 (49.03%) antibiotics were given for duration of 5 days followed by 78 (25%) antibiotics for 7 days, 44 (14.1%) antibiotics for 3 days, 12 (3.84%) antibiotics for 4 days, 8 (2.56%) antibiotics for 1 and 2 days and the least number of antibiotics are given for the durations of 6 days, 8 days and 10 days respectively. Dr Sneha Susanna et al^[16] in their study from Ludhiana showed a much higher prevalence of duration of antibiotic treatment.

Common Surgeries:

In our study, hysterectomy (18.67%) was the most frequent performed surgery type followed by laparotomy (11.33%), fractures (9.33%), appendectomy (8.66%) and other procedures(18%).¹⁷ But in the prospective observational study conducted by Sumit Kumar et al^[12], appendectomy (20%) was the most frequent performed surgery type followed by fractures (14.32%) and hysterectomy, dermatological procedures, genitourinary procedures (13%). Possible Drug-Drug Interactions:

In our study, out of 150 prescriptions, a total of 119(79.33%) drug-drug interactions(DDI's) were found which include 67 minor DDI's which was found to be more than 49 moderate DDI's and 3 major DDI's. Lack of awareness, ignorance, disagreement with the guideline, or different kinds of thought could be the reasons for this. In the study conducted by Bangari Anilkumar et al^[1] out of 94 prescriptions, a total of 24(25.52%) drug-drug interactions were found which is much less as compared to our result.

Antibiotics usage on rationality parameters:

Out of 150 prescriptions included for the study, a total of 24 (16%) medication errors which include 22 (14.67%) dose errors and 2 (1.33%) duplication errors were found. This correlates to the study conducted by Bangari Anil Kumar et al^[1] where they observed a total of 11 (11.7%) medication errors out of 94 prescriptions which include 7 (7.45%) dose errors and 4 (4.25%) duplication error.

CONCLUSION

Surgery is a technology consisting of a physical intervention on tissues. Surgical wound infections are those infections which are confined to the incisions and involving structures adjacent to the wounds that were exposed during operation. Hospital acquired surgical site infection (SSI) is one of the major health problems throughout the world and is a serious complication affecting hospitalized patients¹⁸. Antibiotics can be defined as the variety of substances produced by or derived from certain fungi, bacteria, and other organisms, that can destroy or inhibit the growth of other microorganisms. Surgical antibiotic prophylaxis is defined as the use of antibiotics to prevent infections at the surgical site¹⁹.

- Prescription analysis shows the way towards rational use of drugs. During surgical management of diseases, irrational prescription may lead to severe complications in pre and postoperative management such that even mortalities may occur.
- In our study, a total of 150 cases were collected and from that we conclude that the mostly prescribed antibiotic class in post-operative patients was cephalosporin followed by metronidazole.
- The most common type of surgery was general surgery followed by OBG surgery.
- Regarding gender, the total percentage of male patients were comparatively more than of female post-operative inpatients while the patients in age group 41-50 years were more.
- Maximum no. of antibiotics were given for the five days of duration of treatment.
- Our study suggests that number of Major, Minor and moderate drug interactions, medication errors were high.
- The ASHP guidelines adherence rate pertaining to the antibiotic uses in surgical prophylaxis was fair. Lack of awareness, ignorance, disagreement with the guideline, or different schools of thought could be the reasons for non-adherence; this requires further exploration.
- In addition, Continuous medical education with a focus of rational drug use and evidence based medicine should form part of the program of the hospital.

To conclude, this study provides insights into the patterns of antibiotic use, appropriateness of prescriptions and rationality of antibiotics in post operative patients using ASHP guidelines based on feedback from the study.

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